

SOFTWARE DEFINED RADIO FOR GOVERNMENT AND MILITARY APPLICATIONS

Helena Schwartz

SUMMARY

Software defined radio (SDR) is the process of replacing traditional radio frequency hardware with functional coding. The advantages of SDR are: Increased flexibility in use cases out of a single piece of hardware, lower costs than the fully hardware versions that achieve the same functions, discrete packaging, lower power usage, ease of systems integration, and the ability to maximize the physics involved. For the novice or hobbyist, software defined radio allows for low cost exploration into the radio world. For the Military and Government user software defined radio allows for multipurposing of already owned equipment and the ability to achieve unique goals limited only by the imagination of the programmer. This paper sets out to define software defined radio, its functions, and specific benefits unique to the Government/Military user. This paper infers the reader has an intermediate level understanding of Radio Frequency Engineering and Principles.

DEFINITIONS

The following definitions come from The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) P1900.01 and are provided to ease confusion of multiple meanings.¹

Radio - 1) Technology for wirelessly transmitting or receiving electromagnetic radiation to facilitate transfer of information.

2) System or device incorporating technology as defined in (1).

Radio Node - A radio point of presence incorporating a radio transmitter or receiver.

Software – Modifiable instructions executed by a programmable processing device.

Physical Layer – The layer within the wireless protocol in which processing of RF, IF, or baseband signals including channel coding occurs. It is the lowest layer of the ISO 7-layer model as adapted for wireless transmission and reception.

Data Link Layer – The protocol responsible for reliable frame transmission over a wireless link through the employment of proper error detection and control procedures and medium access control.

Software Controlled – Software controlled refers to the use of software processing within the radio system or device to select the parameters of operation.

Software Defined – Software defined refers to the use of software processing within the radio system or device to implement operating (but not control) functions.

Software Controlled Radio – Radio in which some or all of the physical layer functions are software controlled.

¹ (Travis F. Collins, 2018)

Software-Defined Radio (SDR) – Radio in which some or all of the physical layer functions are software defined.

Transmitter – Apparatus producing radio frequency energy for the purpose of radio communication.

Receiver – A device that accepts a radio signal and delivers information extracted from it.

Air Channel – The physical path in a medium between the transmitter and receiver.

Waveform – 1. The set of transformations applied to information to be transmitted and the corresponding set of transformations to convert received signals back to their information content. 2. Representation of a signal in space. 3. The representation of transmitted RF signal plus optional additional radio functions up to and including all network layers.

Components

A radio is any device that transmits or receives a variety of electromagnetic waves. Examples of different types of radios are radar, sensors, sonar, satellite communications, cell-phone towers, and more. Traditional hardware based radios could only perform one or two functions out of the above listed types. Military and Government units would have to waste a lot of their budget purchasing the different hardware. Even after, for example, the satellite communications ground station was purchased the unit would then have to dig into their pockets further for an array of filters, low noise amplifiers, power converters, cryptology devices, and the

vendor specific connectors that always cost way more than they should. In contrast to mission specific hardware-based radios a software defined radio requires only: an input/output or both, a user interface, power, and a processing unit as shown in the figure below.

The input/output device in a SDR fulfills the purpose of getting information to and from the processing unit. Traditional thinking is that an antenna is involved however opening one's mind a myriad of possibilities become apparent. Microphones are in input device that can capture audio and digital modulation codes that are used in IC chip enabled devices for everything from setting off an improvised explosive device to picking a menu option from an automated phone service. A sensitive enough microphone can pick up frequencies that are inaudible to the human ears but still carry important information. An article by Romit Roy Choudhury published in Tech Briefs in 2018 stated:

“Researchers have designed a sound that is completely inaudible to humans (40 Khz or above), yet is audible to any microphone... When conversing, the inaudible signal

translates to white noise in the microphone to prevent unauthorized....recordings.”²

Other common input devices are stored information in the form of files, antennas, optical connections including fiber and free space optical, ethernet, and more. Output devices are medium in which the generated waveform is propagated out of. Antennas are the common transmitter device that comes to mind but they are only one of many. Speakers and headphone outputs of an SDR can be utilized for playing music or activating a DTMF circuit. Optical mediums such as fiber or blinking LEDs are output devices of SDRs. The application of blinking LEDs can be seen around the winter holidays where SDRs are used to create great performances of synchronized lights and sound; think Rockefeller center at Christmas.

User interfaces are the means in which the user interacts with the SDR. By definition any SDR can perform a needed radio task and only awaits the instructions on how to do it. These instructions are provided by the programmer or engineer through coding. The method of coding and interfacing is very much user specific. SDRs can be coded using Python, C++, Verilog, VHDL, C, and any language that exists today. QCL and Cirq are two examples of coding languages that are used for quantum capable processing units within the SDR. The method chosen should be considered carefully based on knowledge level of the programmer, language familiar to the programmer, compatibility, and ease of system integration with existing frameworks, desired level of customization, and computational resources available. As an example, if one was given the following four tasks:

1) Someone asks at a Hobby level, I want to buy an SDR and get started. What do you recommend?

2) System limited to CPU processing only: I want to extract data from a 1M symbol/second QPSK signal with FEC, scrambling and framing.

3) System has CPU and GPUs: I want to process 100MHz of data and detect signals with 100 Hz resolution.

4) System CPU/GPU and can use FPGAs: I want to process 5 GHz of spectrum and detect signals with 100Hz resolution.

The task being requested in all four scenarios can be accomplished by any SDR however the asker identifies themselves as the user. For question number 1 the user would need to consider what they want to do with the SDR and what their budget is. They would then consider what their comfortability is with coding languages and the formulas used in RF applications. If they are unsure then the recommendation may be to start with their home computer and download MatLab Simulink or Gnu radio to start and test their comfort level before committing to purchase. Question number 2, 3, and 4 are again specific to the asker and can be accomplished by any SDR. The user would have to take into account the same considerations as question 1, but this time add in their comfortability with parallel computing and embedded systems. For a user who is not comfortable with the concept of parallel computing and how to be maximize the potential usage they may find a Python based platform such as Google Colab to be a good place to start. The advantage of such is that Python has many libraries that are CUDA enabled and can do the translations easily between python, C++,

² (Choudhury, 2018)

and pre-coded functions to make it all work. Many of these functions are applicable to the DSP world. If the user is fluent in VHDL or Verilog then it would be advantageous for them to utilize the FPGA to complete their task. The important take away from SDR user interface is that the combinations and flexibilities are meant to be user friendly and there is no “right way” to do it.

Power is the second to most important factor in the performance of SDRs and directly effects what capabilities the SDR will have. While the everyday hobbyist usually toils in the HF and Ham Radio frequencies, the Government and Military rely heavily on the SHF and UHF bands over long distances. The goal of the transmitter is to direct enough transmit power (P_t) off a surface (Antenna/Dish) so that the receiving end has a sufficient flux density of the transmitted signal. The flux density (S) is directly proportional to the P_t and inversely proportional to the surface area of the transmitter.

$$s = \frac{p_t}{4\pi r^2}$$

Flux density is the probability of the excited electrons in the waveform being in a specific location at a specific time. As the waveform travels further away from the transmitter the electrons spread out in a magnitude proportional to the distance from the transmitter squared. The further the distance the receiver is, the more spread out the excited electrons will be, and the less signal will be captured. This effect is illustrated in the figure on the right.

The power capability of the SDR needs to be high enough that the user can reach their usage goal. Having a large enough Satellite Antenna Dish will not be enough if the power level at transmission is not sufficient. Achieving the power levels can be done in a variety of ways by exploiting the power formula:

$$P = I \cdot E$$

Where P is the power at the output, I is the current, and E is the voltage level. Higher power levels can be achieved by adding dedicated power supplies to output portion itself or careful manipulation of onboard power. The P_t range needs to be factored in to any SDR system design. At receiving end the power formula:

$$p_r = SA_e$$

More precisely:

$$p_r = \frac{eD^2p_{eff}}{16r^2}$$

Where the power at receive is equal to the efficiency of the antenna (e), multiplied by the Diameter of the antenna squared (D), multiplied by the effective power of the received signal. All of that is divided by 16 radius squared. The receive side must be able to make sense of the waveform by separating the waveform out from noise generated in the Transmitter and Receiver circuit. Power choices in the SDR directly effect the quality of the signal passed on to

³ (Academy)

the processing unit. Power components have their own excited electrons that can interfere with and become part of the processed waveform. Further, side channel leakage and bleed-over from power components can cause jitter in the system. Jitter effects the data on a waveform by distorting the timing or clocking of a waveform.

Figure 1. Clock jitter

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The waveform comes in and is sampled according to a clock rate. Data that is imprinted on a signal with an ideal clock will look like the top line in the figure above. In the case of jitter, the data drifts a little to the left or right of the ideal position. The effects of jitter get worse over longer distances and can result in bits not being sampled or sampled incorrectly as seen in the below eye diagram.

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The signal should have straight lines like a box however we can see that the system clocking is off, drifting to the right on the rise time but correcting itself on the fall time. This is a symptom of jitter where the clocking is distorted in unpredictable ways. Poor power regulation in a SDR system can also add unacceptable noise to the transmit and receive of a waveform wreaking all sorts of havoc. Good power efficiency, isolation, and routing should be a priority in the design of the SDR as a system and adds limitations to what the effective usage case of the SDR will be.

Processing unit of a SDR will directly effect what the SDR system can do. Today's government and military users are dealing with 5G, 4G, optical, MIMO, CDMA and covert comms which have greatly complicated the SDR system requirements. Adding the User's desire of low form factor and portability has forced engineers to up their game. Traditional hardware-based radios required the user to buy multiple expensive filters and change them out for each new application. SDRs allow for easy manipulation of filtering technique with just a few keystrokes. Waveforms are generated and processed by utilizing transformations of matrices. The heavier the computational requirements are the stronger the user's

⁴ (Bi, 2013)

⁵ (Understanding Data Eye Diagram : Retrived from Google Images, n.d.)

processing unit needs to be. For example, a simple FIR filter (finite impulse response) done on a discretely sampled input waveform can be handled by almost any serial/CPU processor. A more complex and effective filter is the Wiener filter that uses minimum mean square error to differentiate between noise and the intended signal especially useful for elimination of Gaussian noise. The Wiener filter is recursive in nature in that the next value is dependent upon the calculation of the last value. The picture below depicts an application of the Wiener filter:

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The above filter is created in the logic of the processing unit. Here the expected incoming signal based on distance * velocity is used to calculate a mean square prior to being directed through the filter. The signal is then sent through a transformation matrices where the expected Gaussian noise is compared against what the actual values are and used to smooth the data. The precalculated mean square is then added to the signal as it exits the Wiener filter and the difference is taken. That difference is then used as a weighting factor and applied to the smoothing function within the filter and possibly a corrective op-amp. The process would be too intensive at real-time speeds for most CPUs to process while also controlling the rest of the SDR. For a case like this a SDR with parallel computing ability is a must. Parallel computing can

⁶ (Haykin, n.d.)

happen in a FPGA, GPU, TPU, and some multi-core CPUs with custom programmed threading. In the case of a GPU, the waveform would enter the parallel processing block from a serial interface. The parallel processor would allocate each value to an applicable sized matrix as shown in the figure on the right and then be able to perform the transform on all of the values at once instead of feeding them through one set at a time.

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The same imaginative algorithms and functions can be use in encrypting and encoding a transmitted waveform. Creative multiplexing of waveforms creating unexpected and hard to intercept shapes:

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The processing unit implemented in the specific SDR set up should be selected with great care. SDR systems that expect to use software defined networking, VM's, or

⁷ (NVIDIA, n.d.)

multiple users can be bogged down to useless if the processing units are not up to task. Directing traffic to fully utilize the potential is an art form in its own. The type of processing architecture will dictate what the SDR functions are, the bandwidth the SDR can utilize, the types of encoding that will be usable, the complexity of algorithms, and if real time streaming/processing is possible.

Packaging

The Government and Military user has an advantage over the hobbyist in that they have most of the equipment needed to build a SDR on hand. The SDR architecture can then be integrated into the existing laptops, desktops, and their power systems. As an example, Spectrafold Technologies makes a Quadrus software defined radio that is loaded onto a PCI interface that can easily be installed onto existing hardware.

The receiver and card use a FPGA and non-blocking switch matrix to direct the incoming waveforms to four dedicated DSP chips. The driver is windows compatible and the API is open source making for easy system integration. For the times when the user does not have what they need available there are many companies who make

incredible military grade portable SDRs that work with available freeware.

One of the best built ready to go units is the Crossbow by PPM systems:

- Product Overview**
The Crossbow multi-role software defined radio scanning/decoding system integrates:
- Complex RF spectrum analysis with clarity
 - Modular and scalable RF Front End Devices (FED)
 - A reconfigurable processing platform (VITA 49 data stream to convey digitised signal and meta data)
 - Application driven – using government proprietary or open standard applications
 - A modular orchestration layer built on COM Express (Computer-On-Module)
 - An intuitive and reconfigurable User Interface (UI)
 - High bright touchscreen
 - Secure and encrypted storage
 - Secure Ethernet and USB
 - Optional 4G backhaul and control (with optional Wi-Fi)
 - Optional fibre optic antenna system for high risk or remote environments.

The Crossbow is a complete SDR system capable of signal analysis, signal generation, RF to fiber conversions, and even Wi-Fi. Most importantly is that it interfaces with opensource and military certified software suites.

Elbit systems has a SDR for every season and terrain. Pictured below is their E-Lynx™ suite of SDRs that are vehicle ready.

The rugged cases are made to withstand the occasional IED blast a vehicle may take and integrate seamlessly with the system power of existing military vehicles. The Elbit suite is made to run on its own metropolitan area network (MAN). Elbit has been around since 1966 and is based out of Israel. Their location allows them to have intimate knowledge of weather and terrain challenges of the Government and Military user. Their systems can all be tailor-made for specific and classified usage.

L3Harris is the merger of two giants in the military communications world. They have combined to make a one stop shop on SDRs and the software suites that run them. Notable is their Embeddable Modular Radio (EMR)

Inside the mysterious silver box is a complete embedded system capable of data, voice, ISR video, and DSP. Tunable is the operating frequency of 225MHz to 2.5GHz, the transmission power of 50mW to 3.2W, GPS, and even dual channel. The embedded system can be integrated into existing hardware such as cellphones or built into a PCI card already tested to MIL STD 461f.

Conclusion

Radio frequency devices and technology have exploded over the first part of the century. Single use hardware no longer satisfies the diverse environments and missions that the Government and Military users face. The boom in software defined radio technology will mean that the user has an expounded capability of DSP, Cyber security, assured comms, integrated sensors, and quick response with less gear and less money. SDRs allow vastly improved speed and accuracy by having the ability to apply computationally complex formulas to their radio needs taking the theoretical realm into reality. The technology can be integrated with hardware already owned by the user or purchased in mission ready condition.

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